

Supplementary Material 1. Search Strategy

Database name: **Medline**

Search performing date: 08/10/2025

Interface: Ovid

Database timeframe: 1946 to 29/09/2025

Search screen: Advanced screen

Search modes: Boolean / Phrase / Proximity

Filters used:

- Cochrane sensitivity and precision maximising search filter for randomised controlled trials - Glanville J, Kotas E, Featherstone R, Dooley G. Which are the most sensitive search filters to identify randomized controlled trials in MEDLINE? J Med Libr Assoc 2020;108:556–63. <https://doi.org/10.5195/jmla.2020.912>.
- Wright and Jones search filter for older adults (over 50 years of age) - Wright JM, Jones D. Search strategies to investigate decision making by older adults and appraisal by GPs following cancer symptoms 2021. <https://doi.org/10.5518/1034>.

No #	Search	Results
1	resistance training/	14739
2	weight lifting/	5367
3	((weight\$ or power\$) adj2 lift\$).tw.	2350
4	(weightlift\$ or powerlift\$).tw.	1706
5	((resistance or resistive or strength\$ or weight\$ or bodyweight or body weight or anaerob\$) adj2 (coach\$ or train\$ or exercis\$ or conditioning or workout\$ or program\$)).tw.	52691
6	(progressive adj2 (overload\$ or resistance)).tw.	1880
7	(calisthenic\$ or callisthenic\$).tw.	330
8	1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 6 or 7	60321
9	endurance training/	793
10	cardiorespiratory fitness/	4105
11	high-intensity interval training/	2914
12	((aerob\$ or cardio\$ or respirat\$ or endur\$) adj2 (coach\$ or train\$ or exercis\$ or activit\$ or workout\$ or fitness or program\$)).tw.	80687
13	(HIIT or HIIE).tw.	3414
14	((high or low or medium or moderate) adj2 intens\$ adj2 (train\$ or exercis\$ or activit\$ or workout\$)).tw.	20963
15	((gait or walk\$ or treadmill\$ or BWSTT or ambulat\$ or cycl\$ or ergomet\$ or run\$ or jog\$ or elliptic\$ or bike or bicycl\$ or cycl\$ or swim\$) adj2 (coach\$ or train\$ or exercis\$ or activit\$ or workout\$ or program\$ or fitness\$)).tw.	81567
16	9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13 or 14 or 15	167999

17	exp Aged/	3764745
18	elderly.tw,kw.	325524
19	geriatric*.tw,kw.	88747
20	senior.tw,kw.	48995
21	(older adj (adult? or m#n or wom#n or person? or people)).tw,kw.	225715
22	Geriatrics/	32130
23	(Age? adj3 (over or older) adj2 (5# or 6# or 7# or 8# or 9#)).tw.	63806
24	sexagenarian.tw,kw.	82
25	septuagenarian.tw,kw.	277
26	octogenarian.tw,kw.	2045
27	nonagenarian.tw,kw.	843
28	centenarian.tw,kw.	1021
29	gerontolog*.tw,kw.	9950
30	(">=5# years old" or ">5# years old").tw.	20016
31	(">=6# years old" or ">6# years old").tw.	32083
32	(">=7# years old" or ">7# years old").tw.	18812
33	(">=8# years old" or ">8# years old").tw.	11537
34	(">=9# years old" or ">9# years old").tw.	3830
35	17 or 18 or 19 or 20 or 21 or 22 or 23 or 24 or 25 or 26 or 27 or 28 or 29 or 30 or 31 or 32 or 33 or 34	4021905
36	exp randomized controlled trial/	649290
37	controlled clinical trial.pt.	95742
38	randomized.ab.	712020
39	placebo.ab.	262627
40	clinical trials as topic.sh.	205896
41	randomly.ab.	470482
42	trial.ti.	347605
43	36 or 37 or 38 or 39 or 40 or 41 or 42	1718986
44	exp animals/ not humans.sh.	5381851
45	43 not 44	1585871
46	8 and 16 and 35 and 45	1696

